

Supplementary appendix

A global *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* genomic framework sheds light on current diphtheria reemergence

Authors

Melanie Hennart^{a,b,c}, Chiara Crestani^a, Sebastien Bridel^a, Nathalie Armatys^{a,b}, Sylvie Brémont^{a,b}, Annick Carmi-Leroy^{a,b}, Annie Landier^{a,b}, Virginie Passet^{a,b}, Laure Fonteneau^e, Sophie Vaux^e, Julie Toubiana^{a,b,d}, Edgar Badell^{a,b} and Sylvain Brisse^{a,b,*}

Affiliations

^a Institut Pasteur, Université Paris Cité, Biodiversity and Epidemiology of Bacterial Pathogens, F-75015, Paris, France

^b Institut Pasteur, National Reference Center for Corynebacteria of the Diphtheriae Complex, Paris, France

^c Sorbonne Université, Collège doctoral, F-75005 Paris, France

^d Department of General Pediatrics and Pediatric Infectious Diseases, Hôpital Necker-Enfants Malades, APHP, Université de Paris, Paris, France

^e Santé publique France, Saint-Maurice, France

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57

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61 *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* lineages Mitis and Gravis

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Figure S1. Epidemiological curve of *tox*-positive *C. diphtheriae* infections in France
 A. Number of reported cases by year, France, 2002-2022; B. Number of reported cases by week, France, 2022. The cases were either from metropolitan France, or overseas territories (see color key).

*CdSC: *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* species complex

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Figure S2. Flowchart of the main analytical steps of DIPHTOSCAN

DIPHTOSCAN starts with a taxonomic check, and then proceeds to virulence genes detection (including the *tox* gene, and its possible truncations), resistance features (genes and mutations, and their co-localization), and biovar-associated genes (*spuA* and *nar* clusters). Optionally, the presence of integrons is detected, and a k-mer distance-based tree can be built.

- blastn.py
- misc.py
- truncation.py
- mlstBLAST.py
- species.py*
- __main__.py*

download_alleles_st.py*

tool → database → AMRFinderPlusdatabase*

→ .amrfinder

*with some modifications


```

|- /diphtOscan
  |- function __main__.py
  |- species
  |- get species
  |- mlst
  |- get profile MLST
  |- get ST
  |- resistance / virulence
  |- get resistance and virulence gene
  |- get genomic context
  |- prediction
  |- get prediction tox-NTTB
  |- get biovar loci
  |- integron
  |- get integronfinder2
  |- tree
  |- get Jolytree

|- data
  |- ... →

|- module
  |- species
  |- download_alleles_st
  |- mlstBLAST
  |- toxBLAST
  |- blastn
  |- misc
  |- truncation

|- data
  |- species
  |- ReferenceCorynebacterium
  |- C.belfantii_FRC0043T.fasta
  |- C.belfantii_FRC0301.fasta
  |- C.diphtheriae_NCTC11397T_mitis.fasta
  |- C.diphtheriae_NCTC13129_gravis.fasta
  |- C.diphtheriae_PW8_mitis.fasta
  |- C.pseudotub_ATCC19410T.fasta
  |- C.pseudotub_MB302_NZ_CP021982.fasta
  |- C.rouxii_FRC0190T.fasta
  |- C.rouxii_FRC0297.fasta
  |- C.silvaticum_KL0182T.fasta
  |- C.striatum_ATCC6940T.fasta
  |- C.striatum_KGNa-01.fasta
  |- C.ulcerans_FRC0011.fasta
  |- C.ulcerans_FRC0058.fasta
  |- C.ulcerans_NCTC7910T.fasta

  |- mlst
  |- atpA
  |- dnaE
  |- dnaK
  |- fusA
  |- leuA
  |- ocbA
  |- rpoB
  |- MLST profile and ST

  |- resistance
  |- 2022-08-09.1
  |- Corynebacterium_diphtheriae (see custom list)
  |- virulence (see custom list)

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Figure S3. Bioinformatics tools integrated into DIPHTOSCAN

DIPHTOSCAN is a pipeline which groups a set of novel scripts and adaptations of previous tools, including Kleborate, BIGSdb, AMRFinderPlus and IntegronFinder2.

Custom features of DIPHTOSCAN

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82 **Figure S4. Custom features of DIPHTOSCAN database**

83 Description of the custom features of the DIPHTOSCAN database. The database was built by
 84 adding to the AMRFinderPlus database, *ad-hoc* resistance and virulence genes, as well as
 85 molecular determinants to predict the biovar.

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87 **A. Effect of deduplication of the global dataset**

88

89 **B. Sublineage representation in France-2022 versus the**
 90 **deduplicated dataset**

91

92 **Figure S5. Sublineage frequency comparisons between datasets**

93 **A.** Effect of deduplication of the global dataset. X-axis: The number of isolates in the entire
 94 global dataset (n=1,249 genomes). Y-axis: The number of isolates in the deduplicated global

95 dataset (n=976). Each sublineage is represented as a circle; the main sublineages' identifiers
96 are shown.

97 **B.** Sublineage representation in France-2022 *versus* the global (deduplicated) dataset. X-axis:
98 The number of isolates in the deduplicated dataset (n=976 genomes). Y-axis: The number of
99 isolates in the France-2022 dataset (n=101). Each sublineage is represented as a circle; the main
100 sublineages' identifiers are shown.

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104 **Figure S6. Phylogenetic tree of 1,350 *Corynebacterium diphtheriae***

105 The tree shows the placement of the France-2022 isolates (n=101) within the diversity of the
 106 1,249 global non-duplicated genomes. The tree was generated using JolyTree (Criscuolo,
 107 2020). The scale bar represents the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The first circle
 108 indicates the dataset, with France-2022 isolates indicated with light-blue rays from the tree
 109 leaves, and a blue color gradient (darker blue for older isolates) for French NRC isolates prior
 110 to 2022. Grey color sectors correspond to the global genomes. The second inner circle indicates
 111 sublineage alternation; main sublineages are labeled within the sectors. The following circle
 112 indicates the presence, disruption or absence of the diphtheria toxin *tox* gene (see key).

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129 **Figure S8. Phylogenetic tree of amino acid-translated *tox* alleles found in the 1350**
 130 **genomes dataset.**

131 The Neighbor-Joining tree was built based on amino acid-translated *tox* alleles. The scale bars
 132 give the number of substitutions, as indicated above the branches. These leaves are labeled with
 133 integer numbers, which correspond to the *tox* alleles from the BIGSdb nomenclature
 134 ([https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/cgi-](https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdb/bigsdb.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=alleleQuery&locus=tox&submit=1)
 135 [bin/bigsdb/bigsdb.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=alleleQuery&locus=tox&submit](https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdb/bigsdb.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=alleleQuery&locus=tox&submit=1)
 136 [=1](https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdb/bigsdb.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=alleleQuery&locus=tox&submit=1)); and the groups indicated after the leaves are those given in the study by Will *et al.*, 2021
 137 (DOI: [10.1038/s41467-021-21870-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21870-5)). The correspondence between the *tox* alleles of this study
 138 and that of Will *et al.*, 2021, was achieved by using the common isolates available in the
 139 genomic dataset; *tox* alleles with no correspondence shown here, were not present among the
 140 isolates studied in Will *et al.*

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143 **Figure S9. Sublineage distribution of resistance features, including *pbp2m* and *ermX***

144 (Top) The bars height corresponds to the number of genomes per sublineage (entire dataset,
 145 1,249 isolates). Bars are colored according to the resistance score, i.e. the number de resistance
 146 families present in the strains (see color key).

147 (Bottom) Same as in A, with genomes carrying genes associated with resistance to penicillin
 148 (PEN.) and/or erythromycin (ERY.) resistance being colored (see key).

149

150 **Figure S10. Phylogenetic distribution of iron metabolism and adhesion-associated genes**
 151 **in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* lineages Mitis and Gravis**

152 The tree was obtained by maximum likelihood based on a multiple sequence alignment of the
 153 core genome (as in main Figure). The scale bar gives the number of nucleotide substitutions
 154 per site. The main lineages Mitis and Gravis are drawn using purple and green branches,
 155 respectively. The first inner circle indicates the presence of the *spuA* gene (darker color:
 156 presence). The four following circles indicate the presence of the heme metabolism-associated
 157 genes *chtAB*, *htaA*, *htaB* and *htaC*. The three following circles indicate the presence of the iron
 158 metabolism-associated genes: *irp1ABCD*, *irp2ABCDEFGHI-irp2JKLMN* and *iusABCDE*. Next,
 159 three following circles indicate the presence of the fimbriae gene clusters: SpaA-type, SpaD-
 160 type and SpaH-type. The most external circle indicates the presence of collagen-binding protein
 161 DIP2093. For circles that represent clusters of genes, a color gradient represents the number of
 162 genes present in the cluster (darker: more genes).